

APPROACHES AND METHODS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: Currently, in our country, a lot of attention is paid to the use of various innovative and pedagogical technologies in teaching English in general schools and educational institutions. This article is devoted to the methodology of teaching English in classes.

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda mamlakatimizda umumta'lim maktablari va ta'lim muassasalarida ingliz tilini o'qitishda turli innovatsion va pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanishga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Ushbu maqola sinflarda ingliz tilini o'qitish metodikasiga bag'ishlangan.

Аннотация: В настоящее время в нашей стране большое внимание уделяется использованию различных инновационных и педагогических технологий при преподавании английского языка в общеобразовательных школах и учебных заведениях. Данная статья посвящена методике преподавания английского языка на уроках.

Key words: Pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, "Boomerang" method, approach, basic classification, *functional methods*, *interactive methods*.

Language teaching methods are dependent on and influenced by different theories of language and language learning. The history of language teaching puts forward different kinds of methods. These methods are adopted by different people in different situations according to the need of the learners. Different methods may be appropriate to different contexts. The efficiency of a method depends upon a complex of factors which vary from place to place and situation to situation. The challenge today is to avoid dogma and rigidity through fresh consideration of priorities, and to root all new strategies in the realities of the situation. An attempt has been made here to take into sweep the history of language teaching methods beginning from the

earliest times to the present time. Some of the important methods and approaches to teach English as a second language are discussed here. The field of linguistics and teaching in the 20th century is marked by the development of different **foreign language teaching** methods and approaches. Some have either no, or a small following and others are widely used. Although modern foreign language teaching has adopted completely new methods, the work of language professionals in the period between 1950 and 1980 contributed significantly to scientific views in the field of **second language teaching** and learning. Even when methods are not frequently used or have fallen into obscurity, they may offer useful insights into the general **teaching** methodology. Surely, modern teaching is also based on the elements derived from these methods. Basic classification of methods falls into three main categories: (1) Structural methods: the grammar-translation method and the audio-lingual method (2) Functional methods: situational language teaching (3) Interactive methods

Structural Methods

The Grammar-Translation Method

This foreign language teaching method is a structural method based on the traditional (also called classical) method of teaching Greek and Latin.

- In the 18th and 19th centuries, an adult was considered mentally prepared for the world and its challenges only if the person had learned classical literature of the Greeks and Romans and mathematics.

The Goal

The goal of the grammar-translation method was to make learners able to read and **translate literary masterpieces** and classics *and not to speak a foreign language*.

It stayed in schools until the 1960s (including American schools), but the evolving teaching methodology found many weak points of this method and it was consequently replaced with the audio-lingual and direct method.

Note: However, India, where a number of methods and techniques have evolved in foreign language teaching, this method is the oldest method of teaching and it is still in active use. The Audio-Lingual Method

In the audio-lingual method, students are taught directly in the target language without using their native language. New words and grammar are explained orally in the target language.

Unlike the direct method, the audio-lingual method doesn't focus much on vocabulary, but on static grammar drills. There is no explicit grammar instruction, just memorizing in form and practicing a certain construction until it is used spontaneously.

- The *innovation*, however, was the use of the *language laboratory* or *lab* (an audio or audio-visual installation aid). In this context, the teacher presents the correct model of a sentence and the students repeat it. The language lab stayed in use in modern teaching, especially to practice listening comprehensions. However, the students exposed to this method have almost no control on their own output and exactly this is in direct opposition to modern language teaching.

An Example of a Functional Method

Situational Language Teaching

In applied linguistics, Situational Language Teaching is considered an oral approach developed by British linguists in the period from 1930s to 1960s. Its main principles are *learning vocabulary* and *practising reading skills*.

This approach (some linguists refer to it as a *method*) has a behavioristic background; it deals less with conditions of learning and more with the processes of learning.

These learning processes are divided into three stages:

1. receiving knowledge,
2. memorizing it by repetition
3. using it in practice to the extent that it becomes a personal skill and habit.

Characteristics of Situational Language Teaching:

- In theory, language learning is a habit-formation, which means mistakes should be avoided as they make bad habits.

- Language skills are presented orally and then in written form as they are learnt more effectively that way.
- The meanings of words are learnt only in a linguistic and cultural context.
- There is strong emphasis on oral practice, thereby this form of teaching still attracts the interest of many practically oriented classroom teachers.

The view of this method was called into question by Noam Chomsky, who in 1957 showed that the structural and behavioristic approaches to language teaching were not right. He claimed that fundamental defining features of a language such as creativity and uniqueness of individual sentences were neglected by their application. He also believed that a learner must have an innate predisposition for a certain kind of linguistic competence.

An Example of an Interactive Method

ART SPIRAL

Skills

Being Creative

Thinking, Decision-Making

What is it?

This activity allows pupils to personally reflect and communicate their thoughts, ideas and feelings in a creative way on a particular issue.

Implications for classroom layout

A large space is needed for ease of movement and interaction. Alternatively, if pupils are seated at desks, they can use an individual piece of paper which can then be made into a group collage/spiral.

How does it work?

1. A large spiral of paper is placed in the centre of an open space. The paper should be large enough to allow for easy movement and space for all pupils' contributions.

2. Everyone in the group selects a free space on the spiral and draws something which represents their thoughts on a particular topic. The pupils might be encouraged to include a few words which spring to mind on the topic beside their drawings.

3. After an allocated time pupils might move onto another free area of the spiral and graphically represent their thoughts on a related issue.

4. After completion of the activity, the facilitator should allow time for pupils to look at the whole spiral and view other people’s contributions. Pupils might be encouraged to develop or add to other people’s contributions.

5. A debrief afterwards might encourage pupils to communicate verbally their initial individual thoughts on the issue and then their emotions after viewing the drawings of the whole class. Were their thoughts and feelings modified as a result? How did they feel if someone developed their own contribution?

In conclusion, it should be said that the teaching of the modern language is aimed at the formation of a more civilized personality, as long as it has the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of the modernization of the entire system. With confidence, teachers can get acquainted with the most advanced approaches, subsequently combine them, and achieve significant growth in the educational system using their work.

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